

Design, Synthesis, Molecular Docking Studies and Antidepressant Activity Profile of Some Novel Isatin Derivatives

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Abstract:-- Within the scope of our new antidepressant drug development efforts, in this study, fifteen novel isatin derivatives VII (a-o) were synthesized by conventional methods. All the synthesized compounds were elucidated by spectroscopic methods. Test compounds were administered orally at a dose of 50 mg/kg to albino rats and albino mice before 24h, before 5h and 1h of performing tail suspension test and modified forced swimming test respectively. The obtained results showed that compounds VIIa (R=H) and VIId (R= 6-Cl) reduced the immobility time of mice as assessed in the tail suspension test. Whereas, in the modified forced swimming test, the same compounds not only significantly decreased the immobility, but also increased the swimming frequencies of mice, without any alternation in the climbing frequencies. Compounds VIId (R=6-Cl), VIIh (R=6-NO₂) and VIIm (R=8-COOH) have shown significant antidepressant activity when compared with standard drug fluoxetine. Docking studies were carried out with Autodock 4.0, using MGL Tools 1,5,6. All the synthesized compounds were docked at the active site of MAO-A enzyme (PDB ID:2BXS). Docking results suggested hydrogen bond interactions between methyl, bromine, chlorine, oxadiazine and imidazolone rings. Among all synthesized compounds, VIIg R=6-Br), VIIe (R=6-CH₃), VIId (6-Cl) and VIIa (R=6-H) have shown highest binding energies i.e., -11.15, -11.03, -10.95 and -10.82 Kcal/mol respectively.

Keywords:--Isatin, Imidazolone, Oxadiazine, Antidepressant and Molecular Docking studies.

I.INTRODUCTION

Depression is a complex disease with heterogeneous pathology and many of the core symptoms such as feeling of hopelessness and low self-esteem are not easily reproduced in animals. Current treatments for depression either fail to produce complete recovery or induce unwanted side effects. So there is still a large unmet clinical need. Clinical data suggests that dopamine is also involved in the pathophysiology and treatment of depression. Medications such as Tricyclic antidepressants (TCAs), Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors (SSRIs), Monoamine Oxidase inhibitors (MAOIs), Serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs), 5-HT₂ receptor antagonists and other heterocyclics are clinically used for drug therapy. Monoamine oxidases (MAO) are a family of enzymes in the CNS that catalyzes the oxidation of or inactivation of biogenic amines. MAO inhibitors act by inhibiting the activity of monoamine oxidase, thus preventing the breakdown of monoamine neurotransmitters and thereby increasing their availability. There are two isoforms of monoamine oxidases like MAO-A and MAO-B. MAO-A preferentially deaminates serotonin, melatonin, epinephrine and norepinephrine. MAO-B preferentially deaminates phenethylamine and certain other trace amines [1]. Those agents that can inhibit the above system can produce beneficial response in the condition of the central nervous system. Particularly MAO-A inhibitors have been employed in the treatment of depression, anxiety and mental disorders while MAO-B inhibitors could be used in the treatment of Parkinson's and Alzheimer's disease. Excessive accumulation of oxidants in the body leads to oxidative stress, which causes neurological disorders. Carotenoids, Vitamin C, Vitamin E etc., present in the diet, have antioxidant properties that lead to the neutralization of active oxidants in the body, but in some acute substances, it is necessary to use antioxidant agents [2-4].

Isatin is a privileged building block with wide pharmacological properties including anti-microbial, anti-convulsant, antidepressant, anti-inflammatory, anti-Parkinsons, and anti-Alzheimer activities. Isatin derivatives, have shown numerous CNS activities. Isatin acts as regulator of the biological system in the brain. The presence of a significant amount of endogenous Isatin in tissues such as the brain is an explanation for the possible role of this substance in central nervous system (CNS) function. Based on the important role of isatin derivatives as effective small molecules with promising biological activity, in this study novel isatin derivatives were subjected to synthesis and further evaluated for antidepressant activity[5-6].

2.MATERIALS AND METHODS

All the materials and reagents were procured from commercial suppliers like Sigma Aldrich and S.D. Fine Chem Ltd and used without purification. Precoated TLC silica gel plates bought from S.D. Fine were used to validate the quality of the substances and progress of the reaction. To purify the reaction mixtures, silica gel 60 F254 was used. The melting points of all compounds were estimated using a capillary tube open type and the EZ Melt automated melting point equipment. All synthesized compounds were characterized by spectral analysis, such as FTIR, ¹HNMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆), and mass spectrometry. The final compounds were docked at the active sites of MAO-A enzyme (PDB ID:2BXS) a widely known enzyme target for depression using AUTODOCK.4.0 software.

3.EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

A. General Procedure

1.Step-I: Synthesis of (4-Aminophenyl)(hydrazinyloxy)methanone (II): The (4-aminophenyl) (hydrazinyloxy) methanone (II) was synthesized by refluxing a mixture of Benzocaine (I) (0.015 mol) with hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) for 3 h (monitored by TLC). The cooled mixture was gradually poured over crushed ice by stirring constantly. The mixture was then allowed to stand, and the solid separated was filtered, washed thoroughly with cold water, dried, and recrystallized from ethanol (Yield: 87.4%, melting point: 81-83°C). [7]

2.Step-II: Synthesis of 3-{2-[4-aminobenzoyl]oxy}hydrazinylidene}-substituted-1,3-dihydro-2H-indol-2-ones (IVa-o): Equimolar quantity (0.01 mol) of (4-aminophenyl) (hydrazinyloxy)methanone (II), substituted isatin (III) (0.01 mol) and few drops (2ml) of glacial acetic acid (0.01 mol) were dissolved in 20 ml of warm methanol and refluxed for 2-4h. After standing for around 24 hours at room temperature, the products formed were separated by filtration, vacuum dried, and recrystallized from warm methanol (Yield: 71.4%, melting point: 238-240°C).

3.Step-III: Synthesis of 4-(substituted[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-yl)anilines (Va-Vo).

Sulphuric acid (2ml) was warmed to 50°C, finely powdered appropriate 3-{2-[4-aminobenzoyl]oxy}hydrazinylidene}-substituted-1,3-dihydro-2H-indol-2-one (IVa-o, 0.001 mole) was added while stirring in small portion at such a rate so as to maintain the temperature between 60°-70°C but not higher. External cooling was applied at this stage to control the temperature. After the addition of compound (IVa-o), the temperature of the solution was raised to 80°C and maintained at that temperature for 10 minutes. Completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC in solvent system 7:3 (Ethyl acetate:Hexane). Then, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into crushed ice while stirring. After standing for about half-an-hour, the excess amount of sulphuric acid was neutralized to litmus with sodium bicarbonate. A solid mass of 4-(substituted [1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-yl) aniline (Va-Vo) were obtained. The obtained precipitate was filtered with suction pump and washed with cold water and dried. It was purified by recrystallization from methanol to get a crystalline solid. (Yield 65%, m.p: 210°C) [8].

4. Step-IV: Synthesis of 2-phenyl-5-benzylidene-3[4-substituted([1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3-yl) phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-ones (VIIa-VIIo): A mixture of equimolar quantities of 4-(substituted [1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-yl)aniline (Va-Vo, 0.01 mol) and 2-phenyl-4-benzylidene-4H-oxazol-5-one (VI) (0.01 mol) [9] was refluxed in sodium acetate (0.01 mol) and glacial acetic acid (2ml) for 8-9h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion of the reaction resulting mass was poured into crushed ice and neutralised with NaHCO₃. Precipitate obtained was filtered, dried and was recrystallized from methanol to get pure novel compounds [10].

Compound-VIIa (R=H): 2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3[4-([1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3-yl) phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one: IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 3083 (-CH Str Aromatic), 2925, 2822 (-CH Str Aliphatic), 1716 (-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1618 (-C=N Str), 1512 (-CH=CH Str), 1458 (-C=C Str aromatic), 1261 (-C-N Str), 1063 (-C-O-C Str). ¹H NMR (DMSO) δ ppm: 9.235 (s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 7.998 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.804 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.732 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.599 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.501 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.500 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.496 (t, 3H, Ar-H), 7.398 (t, 3H, Ar-H), 6.798 (t, 2H, Ar-H). ¹³C NMR (DMSO) δ ppm: 167.0, 150.0, 146.0, 142.8, 138.8, 134.7, 132.7, 131.4, 130.2, 129.9, 128.2, 126.3, 126.1, 54.4. Mass (EI-MS): m/z 494.13 (M+1, 100%).

Compound-VIIb (R=8-Cl): 2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3[4-(8-chloro[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3-yl) phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one: IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 3028 (-CH Str Aromatic), 2968, 2846 (-CH Str Aliphatic), 1728 (-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1601 (-C=N Str), 1506 (-CH=CH Str), 1451 (-C=C Str aromatic), 1250 (-C-N Str), 1085 (-C-O-C Str), 789 (-Cl Str Ar-Cl). ¹H NMR (DMSO) δ ppm: 9.206 (s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.300 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.998 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.821 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.812 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.798 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.698 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.599 (t, 3H, Ar-H), 7.475 (t, 3H, Ar-H). ¹³C NMR (DMSO) δ ppm: 167.7, 151.3, 142.2, 139.5, 136.8, 135.2, 134.5, 133.8, 131.6, 130.6, 129.2, 128.4, 127.5, 125.8, 53.4. Mass (EI-MS): m/z 528.21 (M+1, 100%), 529 (M+2, 30%).

Compound-VIIc (R=8-CH₃): 2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3[4-(8-methyl[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3-yl) phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one: IR (KBr) cm⁻¹: 3053 (-CH Str Aromatic), 2975, 2875, 2736 (-CH Str Aliphatic), 1712 (-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1636 (-C=N Str), 1553 (-CH=CH Str), 1418 (-C=C Str aromatic), 1281 (-C-N Str), 1063 (-C-O-C Str). ¹H NMR (DMSO) δ ppm: 9.234 (s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.179 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 8.300 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.898 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.800 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.698 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.649 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.551 (t, 3H, Ar-H), 7.500 (t, 3H, Ar-H), 7.500 (t, 2H, Ar-H), 7.195 (t, 3H, Ar-H). ¹³C NMR (DMSO) δ ppm: 170.2, 150.1, 145.3, 140.3, 138.7, 134.6, 130.1, 129.2, 127.9, 127.3, 126.1, 124.7, 122.6, 120.2, 55.2, 29.2. Mass (EI-MS): m/z 508.3 (M+1, 100%).

Figure.No.1. Schematic representation of synthesis of 2-phenyl-5-benzylidene-3[4-substituted([1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3-yl) phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-ones VII(a-o)

Table.No.1: Physical Properties of Novel Isatin derivatives VII(a-o)

Compounds	Mol.Formula	R	Mol. Weight(gm)	Colour of the compounds	M.P ($^{\circ}$ C)	% Yield	Rf value
VIIa	C ₃₁ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₂	H	493.15	Orange	217-219	86	0.67
VIIb	C ₃₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₅ O ₂	8-Cl	527.11	Pale green	235-237	79	0.81
VIIc	C ₃₂ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂	8-CH ₃	507.17	Red	191-193	85	0.71
VII d	C ₃₁ H ₁₈ ClN ₅ O ₂	6-Cl	527.11	Green	219-221	77	0.66
VII e	C ₃₂ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₂	6-CH ₃	507.17	Brick red	213-215	81	0.56
VII f	C ₃₁ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₂ F	6-F	511.14	Creamish yellow	177-179	79	0.75
VII g	C ₃₁ H ₁₈ BrN ₅ O ₂	6-Br	571.06	Yellow	247-249	74	0.83
VII h	C ₃₁ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄	6-NO ₂	538.14	Thick yellow	254-256	78	0.74
VII i	C ₃₃ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₄	6-COOCH ₃	531.16	White	218-220	80	0.71
VII j	C ₃₁ H ₁₈ FN ₅ O ₂	8-F	511.14	Pale orange	203-205	83	0.59
VII k	C ₃₁ H ₁₈ BrN ₅ O ₂	8-Br	571.06	Light yellow	213-215	76	0.62
VII l	C ₃₁ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₄	8-NO ₂	538.14	Thick yellow	236-238	79	0.74
VII m	C ₃₂ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄	8-COOH	537.14	Brown	179-181	83	0.71
VII n	C ₃₄ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₄	8-COOC ₂ H ₅	565.18	Brownish red	187-189	77	0.83
VII o	C ₃₁ H ₁₇ ClFN ₅ O ₂	7-Cl, 8-F	545.11		231-233	76	0.73

Compound-VII d (R=6-Cl): 2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3-[4-(6-chloro[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3yl)phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one. IR(KBr)cm⁻¹: 3102(-CH Str Aromatic), 2989, 2868, 2782(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1721(-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1621(-C=N Str), 1549(-CH=CH Str), 1412(-C=C Str aromatic), 1278(-C-N Str), 1082(-C-O-C Str), 798(-Cl Str Ar-Cl). ¹HNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 9.4023(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.0322-8.0012(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.9903-7.9120(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.7985-7.7122(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.5986-7.5024(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.3874-7.3023(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.2983-7.2092(t, 3H, Ar-H), 7.1902-7.1002(t, 3H, Ar-H), 6.9782-6.9120(t, 1H, Ar-H). ¹³CNMR((DMSO) δ ppm: 172.5, 152.5, 146.8, 142.6, 137.1, 130.7, 129.5, 128.9, 126.1, 125.2, 124.0, 122.1, 120.5, 119.4, 58.2. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 528.23(M+1, 100%), 529.19(M+2, 30%).

Compound-VII e (R=6-CH₃): 2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3-[4-(6-methyl[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3yl)phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one. IR(KBr)cm⁻¹: 3087(-CH Str Aromatic), 2987, 2860, 2748(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1719(-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1624(-C=N Str), 1541(-CH=CH Str), 1420(-C=C Str aromatic), 1276(-C-N Str), 1081(-C-O-C Str). ¹HNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 9.3802(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.1092-8.1002(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.9987-7.9143(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.7342-7.6984(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.5343-7.5023(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.3984-7.2983(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.1983-7.1204(t, 3H, Ar-H), 7.0232-7.0012(t, 3H, Ar-H), 6.873-6.7987(t, 1H, Ar-H). ¹³CNMR((DMSO) δ ppm: 168.4, 156.3, 144.4, 143.2, 140.7, 136.3, 133.6, 130.8, 128.2, 126.9, 125.2, 123.1, 120.3, 119.3, 118.4, 52.8, 28.3. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 508.3(M+1, 100%).

Compound-VII f (R=6-F): 2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3-[4-(6-fluoro[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3yl)phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one. IR(KBr)cm⁻¹: 3032(-CH Str Aromatic), 2977, 2858, 2778(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1708(-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1610(-C=N Str), 1562(-CH=CH Str), 1420(-C=C Str aromatic), 1289(-C-N Str), 1067(-C-O-C Str), 824(-F Str Ar-F). ¹HNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 9.2903(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.1902-8.1243(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.9102-7.8943(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.7483-7.7102(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.4563-7.3923(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.2983-7.2093(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.1892-7.1453(t, 3H, Ar-H), 7.0983-7.0022(t, 3H, Ar-H), 6.8972(t, 1H, Ar-H). ¹³CNMR((DMSO) δ ppm: 170.3, 150.2, 144.1, 140.8, 138.3, 132.6, 130.1, 129.2, 127.3, 126.4, 123.1, 122.4, 119.7, 117.3, 57.4. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 512.32(M+1, 100%).

Compound-VII g (R=6-Br): 2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3-[4-(6-bromo[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3yl)phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one. IR(KBr)cm⁻¹: 3110(-CH Str Aromatic), 2956, 2834, 2792(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1717(-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1634(-C=N Str), 1534(-CH=CH Str), 1416(-C=C Str aromatic), 1283(-C-N Str), 1098(-C-O-C Str), 832(-Br Str Ar-Br). ¹HNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 9.2983(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.1873(s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.8832-7.7802(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.7998-7.7768(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.51982-7.5453(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.4984-7.4192(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.2984(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.1873-7.1793(t, 3H, Ar-H), 7.0954-7.0032(t, 1H, Ar-H). ¹³CNMR((DMSO) δ ppm: 167.3, 154.1, 148.4, 145.3, 138.3, 132.8, 130.7, 130.1, 129.2, 126.3, 123.2, 121.6, 119.9, 115.2, 58.3. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 572.32(M+1, 100%), 573.10(M+2, 30%).

Compound-VII h (R=6-NO₂): 2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3-[4-(6-nitro[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3yl)phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one. IR(KBr)cm⁻¹: 3098(-CH Str Aromatic), 2988, 2868, 2789(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1710(-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1645(-NO₂ Str Ar-NO₂), 1621(-C=N Str), 1528(-CH=CH Str), 1426(-C=C Str aromatic), 1276(-C-N Str), 1032(-C-O-C Str). ¹HNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 9.1982(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.2083-8.1982(d, 2H, Ar-H), 8.1092-8.0232(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.9875-7.9321(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.6754-7.6102(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.5643-7.5293(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.3452(t, 1H, Ar-H), 7.2093-7.1192(t, 3H, Ar-H), 7.1092-7.0045(t, 3H, Ar-H). ¹³CNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 174.2, 159.1, 150.3, 148.2, 140.4, 138.1, 135.3, 134.3, 130.5, 128.1, 125.5, 123.1, 120.2, 119.3, 56.8. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 539.32(M+1, 100%).

Compound-VII i (R=6-COOCH₃): 3-[4-(5-Oxo-2-phenyl-5-benzylidene-1H-imidazol-1-yl)phenyl] [1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-6-methyl carboxylate. IR(KBr)cm⁻¹: 3109(-CH Str Aromatic), 2976, 2878, 2782(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1768(-CO Str Carboxylate), 1723(-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1632(-C=N Str), 1521(-CH=CH Str), 1432(-C=C Str aromatic), 1287(-C-N Str), 1043(-C-O-C Str). ¹HNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 9.3904(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.1982-8.1094(d, 2H, Ar-H), 8.0454-8.0081(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.8976-7.8213(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.7893-7.7043(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.4895-7.4293(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.3982-7.3092(t, 1H, Ar-H), 7.1983-7.1178(t, 3H, Ar-H), 6.9876-6.9034(t, 3H, Ar-H). ¹³CNMR((DMSO) δ ppm: 170.9, 155.3, 152.6, 146.1, 143.7, 137.8, 134.7, 132.0, 131.3, 125.1, 125.5, 123.1, 120.2, 119.3, 57.8, 32.3. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 532.18(M+1, 100%).

Compound-VII j (R=8-F): 2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3-[4-(8-fluoro[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3yl)phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one. IR(KBr)cm⁻¹: 3072(-CH Str Aromatic), 2978, 2876(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1712(-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1623(-C=N Str), 1592(-CH=CH Str), 1438(-C=C Str aromatic), 1284(-C-N Str), 1085(-C-O-C Str), 828(-F Str Ar-F). ¹HNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 9.1983(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.2098(s, 1H, Ar-H), 8.1432-8.1002(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.8754-7.8212(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.7984-7.7234(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.5432-7.5093(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.3874-7.3043(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.2093(t, 2H, Ar-H), 7.1903-7.1202(t, 3H, Ar-H). ¹³CNMR((DMSO) δ ppm: 171.4, 154.3, 152.6, 147.2, 144.9, 140.2, 138.2, 136.4, 128.7, 124.5, 123.2, 121.0, 119.2, 116.3, 54.1. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 512.43(M+1, 100%), 513.

Compound-VII k (R=8-Br): 2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3-[4-(8-bromo[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3yl)phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one. IR(KBr)cm⁻¹: 3104(-CH Str Aromatic), 2988, 2892(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1715(-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1611(-C=N Str), 1587(-CH=CH Str), 1438(-C=C Str aromatic), 1278(-C-N Str), 1093(-C-O-C Str), 812(-Br Str Ar-Br). ¹HNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 9.2562(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.3092(s, 1H, Ar-H), 8.1564-8.1083(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.7862-7.7342(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.6323-7.6232(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.4533-7.3894(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.2893-7.2132(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.0987(t, 2H, Ar-H), 6.9843-6.8654(t, 3H, Ar-H). ¹³CNMR((DMSO) δ ppm: 174.3, 157.1, 153.0, 148.3, 145.7, 138.3, 135.1, 130.2, 126.3, 125.1, 124.1, 120.3, 117.5, 113.7, 56.3. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 572.03(M+1, 100%), 573.14(M+2, 30%).

Figure.No.2. Novel Isatin derivatives VII(a-o)

Compound-VIII(R=8-NO₂):2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3-[4-(8-nitro[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3yl)phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one. IR(KBr)cm⁻¹: 3094(-CH Str Aromatic), 2968, 2843, 2798(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1722(-C=O StrImidazolone), 1638(-NO₂Str, Ar-NO₂), 1621(-C=N Str), 1582(-CH=CH Str), 1443(-C=C Str aromatic), 1299(-C-N Str), 1075(-C-O-C Str). ¹HNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 9.3984(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.2093(s, 1H, Ar-H), 8.1983-8.1203(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.9832(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.7732-7.7094(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.6874-7.6192(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.4896-7.4190(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.2893(t, 2H, Ar-H), 7.12983-7.1098(t, 3H, Ar-H). ¹³CNMR((DMSO) δ ppm: 171.3, 154.2, 148.1, 144.7, 140.2, 135.1, 133.0, 128.7, 125.1, 124.8, 122.0, 121.6, 119.2, 118.5, 58.3. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 539.5(M+1, 100%).

Compound-VIIIm(R=8-COOH):3-[4-(5-Oxo-2-phenyl-5-benzylidene-1H-imidazol-1-yl)phenyl]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-8-carboxylic acid. IR(KBr)cm⁻¹: 3110(-CH Str in Aromatic), 2987, 2867, 2745(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1754(-CO Str Carboxylic), 1702(-C=O StrImidazolone), 1628(-C=N Str), 1543(-CH=CH Str), 1420(-C=C Str aromatic), 1278(-C-N Str), 1054(-C-O-C Str). ¹HNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 10.4654(s, 1H, in Carboxylic group), 9.1983(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.1094(s, 1H, Ar-H), 8.0098-8.0021(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.9854-7.9032(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.7798-7.7922(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.5984-7.5032(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.4103-7.4001(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.2893(t, 3H, Ar-H), 7.1902-7.1009(t, 3H, Ar-H). ¹³CNMR((DMSO) δ ppm: 172.1, 158.4, 154.2, 148.7, 145.2, 138.7, 135.4, 130.1, 129.7, 128.4, 126.8, 122.6, 121.1, 120.4, 56.1, 29.0. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 538.32(M+1, 100%).

Compound-VIIIn(R=8-COO₂H₅):3-[4-(5-Oxo-2-phenyl-5-benzylidene-1H-imidazol-1-yl)phenyl]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-8-ethyl carboxylate. IR(KBr)cm⁻¹: 3097(-CH Str Aromatic), 2987, 2878, 2765(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1767(-CO Str Carboxylate), 1718(-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1628(-C=N Str), 1534(-CH=CH Str), 1442(-C=C Str aromatic), 1292(-C-N Str), 1064(-C-O-C Str). ¹HNMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 9.2983(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.2093(s, 1H, Ar-H), 8.0454-8.0081(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.8043-7.7933(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.6987-7.6532(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.5210-7.5003(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.2983-7.2323(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.0987(t, 3H, Ar-H), 6.8973(t, 3H, Ar-H), 4.5643(q, 2H, -CH₂-), 2.2093(t, 3H, -CH₃). ¹³CNMR((DMSO) δ ppm: 172.4, 154.7, 153.5, 148.2, 145.3, 140.2, 137.2, 136.2, 134.5, 130.2, 128.3, 125.3, 121.6, 120.1, 59.2, 34.6, 28.3. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 567.21(M+1, 100%).

Compound-VIIo(R=8-F,7-Cl):2-Phenyl-5-benzylidene-3-[4-(8-fluoro-7-chloro[1,3,4]oxadiazino[6,5-b]indol-3yl)phenyl]-3,5-dihydro-4H-imidazol-4-one. IR(KBr) cm^{-1} : 3098(-CH Str Aromatic), 2967, 2843, 2756(-CH Str Aliphatic), 1715(-C=O Str Imidazolone), 1616(-C=N Str), 1582(-CH=CH Str), 1415(-C=C Str aromatic), 1278(-C-N Str), 1098(-C-O-C Str), 814(-F Str Ar-F), 798(-Cl Str Ar-Cl). ^1H NMR(DMSO) δ ppm: 9.3653(s, 1H, benzylidene proton), 8.3203(s, 1H, Ar-H), 8.2093(s, 1H, Ar-H), 7.8743-7.8092(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.6754-7.5996(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.4109-7.4003(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.3984-7.3025(d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.2893-7.2032(t, 3H, Ar-H), 7.1092-7.0873(t, 3H, Ar-H). ^{13}C NMR((DMSO) δ ppm: 168.3, 154.4, 148.3, 143.1, 139.6, 133.7, 131.4, 130.1, 129.2, 128.2, 125.3, 124.1, 120.3, 119.9, 55.8. Mass(EI-MS): m/z 546.21(M+1, 100%), 547.32(M+2, 30%).

B. Biological Activity

Animals used: For this experiment, Albino rats (male, weighing around 150-180g) for TST and Albino mice (male, weighing around 20-25g) for FST were used to carry out the antidepressant activity. Animals were kept in polypropylene cages at room temperature, relative humidity and a 12-hrs light/dark cycle. The experiments followed the CPCSEA guidelines. The animals were fed conventional rat chow with ad libitum access to clean tap water [11].

Acute toxicity study: The acute toxicity of the synthesized compounds was investigated in Albino rats and mice using OECD standards 423 [12]. The compounds exhibited toxicity at a dose of 2000mg/kg. Consequently, the safe dose of the drug is 300mg/kg, LD50 value is 850mg/kg. Safe dose of drug was determined using statistical software with linear graph.

I. Antidepressant Activity

Forced Swim test:

Porsolt's behavioural despair or forced swim test (FST): The antidepressant activity of the synthesized derivatives was evaluated by Porsolt's behavioural despair or forced swim test (FST). These behavioral tests are used to assess the efficiency of antidepressant treatments and predict the activity of a wide range of antidepressants, such as MAO inhibitors and atypical antidepressants. For the determination of antidepressant efficacy in humans, they have excellent predictive value[13]. It has been proposed that mice are induced to a characteristic behaviour of immobility when in a small area from which they cannot escape, they are forced to dive. In this test, the mice were independently submerged into a Plexiglas cylinder containing water for 6 minutes. The animals became immobile after the first 2 minutes of the initial intensive combat. They are considered immobile when mice start floating in water in an upright posture with minor movements to avoid sinking and the time of immobility is reported during the last 4 minutes of the 6 min test. This behaviour represents a state of misery that is therapeutically similar to human depression, and can be minimized by many agents. % Duration of immobility was measured in standard group (20mg/kg) and test group (50mg/kg). The standard group received fluoxetine 20mg/kg orally and the synthesized compounds (VIIa, VIIb, VIIc, VIId, VIIe, VIIh, VIIj, VIIm, VIIn, VIIo) were suspended in 1% w/v aq tween 80 and were administered orally to rats at a volume of 0.5 ml/kg body weight.

2. Tail suspension test: For the tail suspension method, male albino rats (150-180g) were divided into three groups, Control, test and standard(n=6/group). Control group received 1% w/v of tween 80 p.o, standard group received Fluoxetine 20 mg/kg, and the synthesized compounds (VIIa, VIIb, VIIc, VIIe, VIIh, VIIj, VIIm, VIIn, VIIo) 50mg/kg were injected (i.p) to rats at a volume of 0.5 ml/kg body weight. Treatment was given 60min prior to the study. Albino rats were suspended on the edge of the table, 50cm above the floor, with the help of adhesive tape placed approximately 1cm from the tip of the tail. The total duration of immobility induced by tail suspension was recorded during a 6 min of 10 min period. Animals were considered to be immobile when it does not show any movement of the body, which when hanged passively and completely motionless [16].

Statistical analysis: All values are represented mean \pm standard error. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to evaluate the data, followed by post hoc Dunnett's multiple comparison test. Significant differences across groups were identified at $p \leq 0.001$ levels. The following formula was used to calculate the percentage decrease in immobility time (%DID) for the test and standard groups.

$$\% \text{ DID} = \left[\frac{A - B}{A} \right] * 100$$

Where A is the duration of immobility (s) in control group(phosphate-buffered saline solution)and B is the duration of immobility(s) in test group[15-16]. Table 2 summarizes all of the antidepressant activity results.

C. Molecular Docking Studies:

The molecular docking studies were performed to investigate the binding mode of target molecules (Fifteen) on selected protein with PDB ID: 2BXS, which is a widely known enzyme target for depression, using Autodock.4.0 software. All the structures of ligand molecules were drawn using chemsketch software. The files are then saved in MDLmol format. The 3D crystal structure of MAO-A enzyme used for docking experiment was obtained from RCSB protein data bank (<http://www.rcsb.org>)with PDB ID 2BXS. The file was saved in PDB format. All the extra chain atoms, cofactors and water molecules were deleted in the first step of protein preparation. In the second, polar hydrogens and missing atoms were added. Kollmann charges were added to the enzyme and the atoms were assigned as AD4 type. Residual charges were spread evenly through the enzyme. The energy minimization was achieved using spdbv software. In all docking tests, the grid box was designed to encapsulate the maximum area of the protein, resulting in blind docking. A grid point's X, Y, and Z axes were assigned the values 60.0 X 60.0 X 60.0. The default grid point spacing was set at 0.4 angstrom. [17].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Chemistry:

A series of some novel Isatin derivatives VII(a-o) were synthesized by a conventional method in four steps. In step one, benzocaine was reacted with hydrazine hydrate to give (4-aminophenyl) (hydrazinyloxy) methanone (II). In step two, Compound II was reacted with substituted Isatins to form 3-{2-[4-aminobenzoyl] oxy} hydrazinylidene}-substituted-1,3-dihydro -2H-indol-2-ones (IVa-IVo) via Schiff's base mechanism. In step three, compounds IVa-IVo underwent cyclization with conc.H₂SO₄ to form (4-(substituted[1,3,4]oxidaizino [6,5-b]indol-yl) anilines(Va-Vo). Finally, in the last step, compounds (Va-Vo) were reacted with 2-phenyl-4-benzylidene-4H-oxazol-5-one (VI) to give the title compounds. All the synthesized compounds gave a good yield and structures were confirmed by FT-IR, ¹HNMR, ¹³CNMR and LC-MS spectral analysis.

B. Pharmacological activity

All the synthesized compounds were evaluated for in vivo antidepressant activity. Mice had free access to food and water before the experiments. Test compounds were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide(2ml) and ethanol (8ml). Fluoxetine was used as positive control. Two in vivo experimental models, FST and TST, were used to estimate the antidepressant activity of synthesized compounds in albino mice and rats respectively.

1. Antidepressant activity:

Forced swim test: Among all synthesized isatin derivatives, compounds (VIIa, VIIb, VIId, VIIe, VIIh, VIIj, VIIm, VIIn, VIIo) were evaluated for their antidepressant activity by FST. Figure 3 displays the acquired results. The resulting values were shown in Table 2. Compounds VIId (R=6-Cl), VIIh (R=6-NO₂) and VIIm (R=8-COOH) have shown significant activity when compared with standard fluoxetine.

Table. No.2: Effect of novel Isatin derivatives (VIIa, VIIb, VIId, VIIe, VIIh, VIIj, VIIm, VIIn, VIIo) in forced swim test(FST).

Name of the compounds	Duration of mobility(Sec) (Mean±S.E.M)	Percentage decrease in immobility duration(%DID)
VIIa	64.03±3.03	25.89
VIIb	59.04±1.32	31.66
VIIc	63.12±1.23	28.01
VIIe	62.12±1.23	28.01
VIIh	35.37±0.01**	59.13
VIIj	58.54±3.43	32.24
VIIk	67.12±1.89	22.3
VIIl	67.12±1.89	22.3
VIIm	42.12±0.03**	51.25
VIIo	58.32±1.32	32.50
VIIp	51.21±01.03	40.72
Vehicle	86.4±3.02	0.00
Fluoxetine (20mg/kg)	20.93±0.54**	75.77

All values indicates mean±standard error of the mean (n=6), **p<0.001 against control.

Figure.No3: Effect of novel Isatin derivatives (VIIa, VIIb, VIId, VIIe, VIIh, VIIj, VIIm, VIIn, VIIo) in forced swim test(FST).

Tail suspension method: The data collected from tail suspension method was graphically represented in Fig.4 and results were summarised in Table.3. Compounds VIId, VIIh, VIIn and VIIm have shown significant activity.

Table. No.3: Effect of novel Isatin derivatives (VIIa, VIIb, VIId, VIIe, VIIh, VIIj, VIIm, VIIn, VIIo) in Tail suspension test(TST).

Name of the compounds	Duration of onset immobility(Sec) (Mean ± S.E.M)	Percentage immobility (%)
VIIa	123.02±3.04	20.59
VIIb	102.43±1.87	33.88
VII d	82.18±0.11**	46.95
VIIe	108.32±3.24	30.08
VIIh	86.42±0.02**	44.21
VIIj	118.34±1.23	23.61
VIII	98.23±2.64	36.59
VII m	102.32±1.82	33.95
VII n	85.24±0.01**	44.98
VII o	87.34±1.04**	43.62
Vehicle	154.93±1.05	00
Fluoxetine (20mg/kg)	73.87±0.12**	52.32

All results indicate the mean±standard error of the mean, n=6, **p<0.001 compared to control.

Figure, No.4: Effect of novel Isatin derivatives (VIIa, VIIb, VIId, VIIe, VIIh, VIIj, VIIm, VIIn, VIIo) in Tail suspension test(TST).

C. Molecular Docking Studies:

The docking results revealed that most of them bind strongly to active site of the enzyme with binding energies ranging from -8.33K.cal/mol to -11.15K.cal/mol. Ligands with R=6-Br and R=6-CH₃ have shown best binding affinities i.e., 11.15K.cal/mol and -11.03K.cal respectively. They formed hydrophobic interaction and hydrogen bonds with MAO-A enzyme's amino acids. This study provided a valuable approach for synthesizing more potent antidepressants.

Table. No.6. Docking scores of novel Isatin derivatives VII(a-o)- Binding Energy(Kcal/mol) and No of Hydrogen bonds.

Compound	R	Binding Energy(Kcal/mol)	No. of H-bonds
VIIa	H	-10.82	2
VIIb	8-Cl	-10.51	3
VIIc	8-CH ₃	-10.57	2
VIIId	6-Cl	-10.95	2
VIIe	6-CH ₃	-11.03	1
VIIIf	6-F	-10.11	3
VIIg	6-Br	-11.15	2
VIIh	6-NO ₂	-10.56	3
VIIi	6-COOCH ₃	-10.48	2
VIIj	8-F	-9.98	1
VIIk	8-Br	-8.33	3
VIIl	8-NO ₂	-10.34	3
VIIm	8-COOH	-10.08	2
VIIIn	8-COOC ₂ H ₅	-10.65	2
VIIo	7-Cl, 8-F	-10.65	1
Clorgylline	-	-7.95	-

Figure.No.7. Docked conformer of compound-VIIe

Figure.No.8. Docked conformer of compound-VIIg

V. CONCLUSION:

In the present investigation, a series of novel Isatin derivatives, VII(a-o) were successfully synthesized with a good yield of 74–86 %. The characterisations of all compounds were performed using different spectral studies. The synthesized compounds exhibited a wide-range of promising antidepressant activity.

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